

ECONOMIC GLOBALIZATION AND GEORGIA**Giguashvili Giuli***PhD in Economics, Professor, Gori State University, Georgia***Makasarashvili Tamar***PhD in Economics, Professor, Gori State University, Georgia***Abstract**

Economic globalization is one of the most important processes in the modern world economy, referring to the integration of national economies into international markets. This process has a significant impact on both developed and developing countries, including Georgia.

The paper aims to analyze the impact of economic globalization on Georgia's economy, assess its positive and negative effects, and identify the main challenges.

The analysis shows that globalization has made a significant contribution to Georgia's economic growth, the attraction of foreign investment, and the expansion of international trade. At the same time, several problems have been identified, such as dependence on external markets, trade deficits, and high vulnerability to global economic shocks.

In conclusion, economic globalization presents both opportunities and challenges for Georgia. It is important for the country to effectively manage global processes, diversify its economy, and enhance its competitiveness.

Keywords: Globalization, Economy, Investments, Trade, Georgia.

Introduction. Economic globalization is the process through which national economies are integrated into the international economic system, manifested in the free movement of goods, services, capital, and technologies. In the modern world, globalization is one of the keys determining factors of economic development, competitiveness, and innovation. For Georgia, a small country with an open economy, globalization acquires particular importance. The country's economic development largely depends on foreign trade, foreign investment, and integration into international markets.

The paper aims to analyze the impact of economic globalization on Georgia's economy, assess its outcomes, and identify the challenges it poses.

Literature Review. The issue of economic globalization has been widely discussed in international academic literature, with particular emphasis on assessing its impact on the economic development of developing countries. According to neoliberal theory, globalization promotes economic growth, market expansion, and the efficient allocation of resources. On the other hand, dependency theory argues that developing countries often become dependent on developed economies, resulting in economic inequality and hindering their independent economic development.

Globalization has three main forms: economic globalization, which is associated with technological, informational, trade, and other types of activities; cultural globalization, which is a result of technological progress and economic globalization; and the third form - political globalization (Giguashvili, 2017:70).

In the context of Georgia, the issue of globalization became particularly relevant in the 1990s, after gaining independence. Studies show that the country's economic liberalization and accession to the World Trade Organization were important steps in integration into the global economy (WTO, 2000).

Based on World Bank data, Georgia is one of the most open economies in the region - the share of foreign trade constitutes a significant portion of gross domestic product (World Bank, 2024). At the same time,

studies indicate that foreign direct investment plays an important role in the country's economic development, especially in the energy and infrastructure sectors (UNCTAD, 2023).

Thus, the analysis of existing literature shows that economic globalization is a multifaceted and complex process that simultaneously encompasses both opportunities and risks. In the case of Georgia, it is an important driver of economic development; however, it requires prudent policy management to mitigate its negative effects.

Georgia's Integration into the Global Economy. The degree of Georgia's integration into global economic processes is clearly reflected in the country's relations with the World Trade Organization and leading international financial institutions. Georgia seeks to become a full-fledged participant and member of global markets. Free trade agreements with the European Union (DCFTA), China, Turkey, and other strategic partners reflect the country's political and economic orientation toward open markets. Its strategic location, at the crossroads of Europe, Asia, and the Middle East, creates an opportunity for the country to develop into a regional logistics and trade hub.

The Impact of Globalization on Georgia's Economy: Economic Growth. In recent years, Georgia's economy has been characterized by a high growth rate. The country's economic dynamics are largely based on the real sector and the expansion of exports (Giguashvili, 2023). In 2024, real GDP growth amounted to 9.7 percent compared to the previous year, reaching 93,022.3 million GEL at current prices (Geostat).

The increased rate of economic growth can be explained by the high level of economic globalization in the country, resulting from the liberalization of tax policy, a liberal international trade policy, the reduction of regulations on business operations, foreign capital, labor, and tourism, and a significant decrease in the level of corruption.

Foreign Trade. One of the main principles of Georgia's economic policy is a liberal foreign trade policy, which implies a simplified foreign trade regime and customs procedures, low import tariffs, and minimal non-tariff regulation. Georgia has one of the most liberal and competitive trade regimes in the world (Giguashvili et al., 2024). In 2024, Georgia's external trade turnover in goods amounted to 23.43 billion USD, representing an 8% increase compared to the same period of the previous year (Geostat).

Foreign Direct Investment (FDI). Foreign investment plays a significant role in Georgia's economy. In the first three months of 2023, the distribution of the largest direct foreign investments by economic sectors looks like this: Manufacturing industry sector -226.3 million dollars (45.6% of total foreign direct investments); Trade sector -90.7 million dollars (18.3%); Transport sector - 43.3 million dollars (8.7%) (Giguashvili et al., 2023). A significant share of investments is directed toward energy, real estate, the financial sector, and tourism (Giguashvili et al., 2025; Salkhinashvili et al., 2023).

Labor Market and Social Effects. Globalization has increased employment opportunities, but it has also intensified competition in the local labor market (Giguashvili et al., 2022). Despite economic growth, unemployment remains a challenge in Georgia. In 2025, according to the National Statistics Office of Georgia, the unemployment rate stood at approximately 12.1%. At the same time, labor migration and remittances represent a significant factor, accounting for approximately 11.9% of GDP (Giguashvili et al., 2023^a).

The positive aspects of economic globalization include: a high economic growth rate, attraction of investment, transfer of technologies, and access to international markets. **The negative aspects** include: dependence on external markets, trade deficits, weak competitiveness of domestic production, and vulnerability to global crises. For example, the COVID-19 pandemic reduced Georgia's economy by 6.8%, confirming its sensitivity to global shocks (Giguashvili et al., 2022). **The primary challenges** for Georgia include economic diversification, improving the export structure, and developing innovation and technology. Despite these challenges, the country's geographical location and open economic policy create significant development potential (Giguashvili and Sadagashvili, 2025).

Globalization rankings are determined according to the Globalization Index; the KOF Index of Economic Globalization reflects the degree of countries' integration into the world economy. According to the 2023 index, Georgia ranks 53rd worldwide in overall globalization with a score of 70.3, while in economic globalization alone it holds the 30th position (Shanidze, 2024).

Conclusion. Thus, economic globalization has a significant impact on Georgia's economic development. On the one hand, it increases economic opportunities, investment, and international integration; on the other hand, it creates dependence on external factors. For Georgia, it is important to manage globalization in a way that maximizes its benefits while minimizing its risks.

References

- Giguashvili, G. (2017). The Socio-Economic Impact of Economic Globalization. THE FUNDAMENTALS OF OUR SPIRITUALITY. Proceedings of the International Scientific Conference Batumi, 15-16 June.
- Giguashvili, G. (2023). Challenges of international migration in Georgia. *Scientific Collection «InterConf+»*, (37(171), 33–43. <https://doi.org/10.51582/interconf.19-20.09.2023.004>
- Giguashvili, G., & Makasarashvili, T. (2022). GEORGIAN LABOR MARKET CHALLENGES IN THE CONTEXT OF THE COVID-19 PANDEMIC. *Scientific Collection «InterConf+»*, (20(105), 37–44. <https://doi.org/10.51582/interconf.19-20.04.2022.003>
- Giguashvili, G., & Makasarashvili, T. (2024). GEORGIAN TRADE POLICY PRIORITIES AND EUROPEAN INTEGRATION. *Grail of Science*, (41), 100–107. <https://doi.org/10.36074/grail-of-science.05.07.2024.012>
- Giguashvili, G., Azmaiparashvili, M., Makasarashvili, T., & Khorguashvili, T. (2022). Aspects of sustainable economic development in post-pandemic Georgia. *ISJ Theoretical & Applied Science*, 02 (106), 573-580. Doi: <https://dx.doi.org/10.15863/TAS.2022.02.106.60>
- Giguashvili, G., Khorguashvili, T., & Makasarashvili, T. (2023a). Mechanisms for managing circular labor migration in Georgia. *Scientific Collection «InterConf+»*, (32(151), 77–88. <https://doi.org/10.51582/interconf.19-20.04.2023.007>
- Giguashvili, G., Makasarashvili, T., Khorguashvili, T., & Orjonikidze, N. (2023). DYNAMICS OF FOREIGN DIRECT INVESTMENTS IN POST-PANDEMIC GEORGIA. *Grail of Science*, (30), 23–31. <https://doi.org/10.36074/grail-of-science.04.08.2023.001>
- Giguashvili, G., Sadagashvili, M. (2025). THE ROLE OF ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF SMART TOURISM. *Journal of Innovative Economics and Management*. Vol 12 No 3 (2025), 119-128. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.46361/2449-2604.12.3.2025.119-128>
- Giguashvili, G., Sadagashvili, M. (2025). THE ROLE OF GEORGIA IN THE MIDDLE CORRIDOR OF THE ANCIENT AND MODERN SILK ROAD, *International Journal of Applied Research and Sustainable Sciences (IJARSS)*. Vol. 3 No. 9, 2025: 777-788. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.59890/ijarss.v3i9.113>
- National Statistics Office of Georgia (2025). <https://www.geostat.ge/>
- Salkhinashvili, M., & Giguashvili, G. (2023). New challenges of the Georgian energy sector and their legal regulation. *Scientific Collection «InterConf+»*, (32(151), 583–593. <https://doi.org/10.51582/interconf.19-20.04.2023.062>
- Shanidze, G. (2024). Business Development in Georgia: The Context of Globalization. Economic

Profile, Vol. 19, 2(28), 79-87. DOI:
<https://doi.org/10.52244/ep.2024.28.07>

13. United Nations Conference on Trade and Development (UNCTAD). (2023). *World Investment Report 2023*. United Nations. <https://unctad.org/publication/world-investment-report-2023>

14. World Bank. (2024). *World development indicators: Georgia*.

<https://data.worldbank.org/country/georgia>

15. World Trade Organization (WTO). (2000). *Georgia and the WTO*. https://www.wto.org/english/thewto_e/countries_e/georgia_e.htm